

THE IMPORTANCE OF GAMES IN THE ACTIVITIES OF A PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION

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Annotation: The article provides information on the development of play activities in preschool children.

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The game is one of the main activities of children with developmental disabilities. The game always reflects real life. Therefore, its content also changes with changes in social life. The game is a conscious activity directed towards a specific goal, which has much in common with labor and serves to prepare young people for labor. On the basis of game activity, the child develops educational activity. Therefore, we should attach importance to the development of children's game activity.

A child never plays silently, even when playing alone, he talks to the toy, communicates with the character he portrays, speaks instead of his mother, patient, doctor, in short, he always speaks himself. Speech helps to better reveal the image. Speech is of great importance in the game process. Through speech, children exchange ideas, share their feelings, experiences. Speech helps to establish friendly relations between children, to treat the surrounding life events and facts in the same

way. The idea, content, game actions, roles, and game rules of a game that arise from the children's own game or are proposed by adults are the aspects that form its structure. The game is real life for the child.

Only if the educator can rationally organize children's games can he achieve positive results. A.P. Usova said: "Correctly organizing the life and activities of children means correctly educating them. The game form of educating children gives effective results because in the game the child does not learn to live, but lives his life." The ability to choose a game is also important. The relationship between the game and education changes as the child grows up. If in a small group the game is the main form of education, then when moving to a large group, the role of education in classes increases.

When children go to the preparatory group, their enthusiasm for schooling awakens. However, the value of play for children does not disappear, but its content changes. Now children are interested in games that require more mental activity, games of a sports nature (with competitive aspects). Play is the main means of educating a child's personality. Through play, children acquire adult work experience, knowledge, skills and abilities, methods of action, moral norms and rules, reasoning and discussions. In play, the child's ways of interacting with peers and adults are formed, feelings and tastes are cultivated. Children's unity in play is divided into several stages.

The first stage is the formation of children's "side-by-side" play. This is typical for children of the first and younger groups. In such a game, children look with interest at their friend's game, play together, and are happy to sit "side by side". The game of children of this age is organized by influencing their behavior under the guidance of adults.

At the second stage, children begin to unite mechanically through the game. Such unions are short-term. By this period, it becomes clear which of the children is interested in which game, if some children are interested in didactic games, others

like active games, and still others prefer creative games, etc.

The task of the educator is to teach children to play this or that game for a longer time. At the third stage, a group of playing children unites through friendly relations and mutual liking for each other. Although the number of players at a time is not large, children play with interest. By this period, a general requirement for evaluating each other arises. At this stage, the educator must create a moral basis for children's unity in the game, form mutual assistance, camaraderie, and friendship in them. To ensure an organized, interesting, and meaningful life for children in kindergarten, it is necessary to use colorful games in age groups. The internal, hidden nature of the rules of creative games creates great freedom for the child to act; his task before the playing team is less ambiguous than in the content of ready-made games with rules. This allows the player to easily change the plot, introduce additional roles. Creative games arouse great interest in children and have a huge impact on them, but it would be a mistake to use only these games in organizing children's lives. Children's mastery of games with rules is of great organizational importance. Rules define certain norms of behavior and the relationship of children to each other, allowing the child to control himself and those playing with him. Independence in following the rules is formed in the process of purposeful upbringing of children in the game.

When a child plays, he or she interacts with a group of children. The social impact of the game, the feelings it evokes, are embodied in the relationships it contains.

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